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NDVI Computation from Hyperspectral Images

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Abstract

Agriculture has witnessed a series technological transformations over time. In recent years, multispectral and hyperspectral satellites have become powerful tools in precision and efficient agricultural practices. Given the richness of information they provide and the fact that multi- and hyperspectral data are not easy to interpret, a consistent visual mapping of these images can be provided for agricultural purposes through vegetation maps. In this paper, we propose and compare alternatives for computing vegetation indices when the data come from hyperspectral images. We provide a comparative analysis, evaluating the distinctions between NDVI maps derived from Sentinel-2 and PRISMA data. The study offers an interpretation of the results and conclusions.

Key words: multispectral images, hyperspectral images, satellite data, NDVI, vegetation maps.

1 Introduction

Agriculture has been vital to human societies for centuries and continues to be indispensable today. Its importance has evolved, and its role is much more than providing food. Agricultural lands can provide biomass for bioenergy [1], and, if managed sustainably, can support a wide range of biodiversity [2] maintaining ecological balance. Also, sustainable farming practices can help carbon sequestration [3], mitigating some of the effects of climate change.

Within this context, assessing the well-being of plants became critically important. Various internal and external factors influence vegetation health. Key internal indicators include chlorophyll content and other elements like carotenoids, anthocyanins, leaf water, nitrogen, lignin, and cellulose. The concentration of these elements within the plants can influence the way the plants absorb light, especially in the blue, red, and near-infrared spectrum. As multispectral (MS) and

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hyperspectral (HS) sensors can capture data across many narrow and contiguous spectral bands, the images they capture can provide distinctive patterns of absorption and reflectance of the different wavelengths of light, known as spectral signatures. By analyzing the spectral signatures of plants across various wavelengths of these images, one can detect the differences and provide insights into the health status of vegetation. These differences in light absorption and reflection serve as valuable information in a series of applications in precision agriculture [4], [5], crop health monitoring [6], irrigation management [7], drought and stress monitoring [8], [9], disease and pest detection [10], land management [11].

Given the significance of these spectral signatures in the interpretation of vegetation health, different vegetation indices have been designed to highlight the various characteristics of plants. These indices, derived from the reflectance values of specific bands in multispectral and hyperspectral images (MSI, HSI), simplify the complexities of the information they contain into numerical indicators. By using different mathematical formulas that use the amplitudes of particular bands that correspond to regions of the spectrum where the vegetation has distinct reflective properties, vegetation indices like the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) can provide valuable insights into the overall health and other specific characteristics. Therefore, for each pixel in an MSI or HSI, a dimensionality reduction of the associated MSI or HSI vector can be performed, and the information can be transformed into a set of vegetation indices that is easier to process, analyze, and interpret. As vegetation indices are numerical measures, they can be integrated into vegetation maps once computed. The vegetation maps can be used to monitor the vegetation status of agricultural crops. The present paper aims to compute NDVI from hyperspectral images and compare it to classical NDVI computed on MSIs.

The article is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the MS and HS images used in our experiments, underlining some of the alternatives in computing vegetation indices when working with multi-source data. Section 3 presents the experimental results. The conclusions and further directions are emphasized in Section 4.

2 Materials and Methods

The research conducted in this paper focused on the images acquired on one site, located in the north of Brasov county, Romania, at 25°36'26" E longitude and 45°38'51" N latitude, corresponding to an area of 30 km × 30 km.

2.1 Data description

In this paper we use two types of data, multispectral and hyperspectral images as described below.

The multispectral image is a Level 2A product of a raw image collected on 24 March 2023 by the Sentinel-2 satellite system. Sentinel-2 is based on the simultaneous operation of two identical satellites having an offset of 180°, each

one equipped with a multispectral instrument for image acquisition, covering both the visible and infrared domains. The instruments measure the Earth's radiance through the atmosphere in 13 spectral bands, and their spatial resolution varies depending on the band [12]. The two satellites combined can provide images of the same location on Earth every five days, making Sentinel-2 system especially useful for agricultural monitoring, where changes can occur rapidly. As standard Sentinel-2 image covers an area of approximately 290 km in width on the ground a preprocessing step in this case was to resample it. The data that was originally at a 10m resolution was resampled to a 30m resolution using SNAP [13].

The image from the PRISMA satellite was collected also on 24 March 2023. PRISMA is a satellite developed by the Italian Space Agency (ASI) for Earth observation and it is designed to capture hyperspectral images of the Earth's surface in 239 spectral bands spanning from 400 to 2500 nm, covering the visible, near, and shortwave-infrared ranges, and thus providing detailed information about its composition and characteristics. The spectral bands are more densely sampled for the Visible Near Infra Red (VNIR) range, 400 nm to 1010 nm. This high sampling rate allows for detailed analysis of features such as vegetation health, water content, and soil properties. On the other hand, for the Short Wave Infra Red (SWIR) range, 920 nm to 2500 nm, the bands have a lower density of spectral sampling compared to the VNIR bands, but they are still useful for identifying specific signatures of minerals, moisture content, and certain vegetation characteristics. The ground sampling distance of the satellite is 30 m, and PRISMA images typically have a resolution of 1000×1000 pixels [14]. For comparison, three product levels of the raw PRISMA image were used: Level 1 (L1), Level 2B (L2B) and Level 2C (L2C). L1 provides a top of the atmosphere spectral radiance. Level 2B provides data on the Earth's surface-reflected radiance, while Level 2C offers insights into the boundary reflection coefficient, aerosol optical thickness, and water vapor mapping. Both of them are atmospheric corrections of the L1 product.

The RGB visualization of the Sentinel-2 and of the PRISMA L2C products is presented in Figure 1. The visualization was done using band selection. A subsequent processing of the images by contrast enhancement and color correction was performed out of aesthetic reasons.

2.2 Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

Vegetation indices are numerical values, computed by mathematical combinations of the amplitudes of various wavelengths of light captured by remote sensing devices. They quantify different aspects of vegetation health, abundance, and photosynthetic activity. Since different aspects of plants, including their species characteristics, physiological conditions, and stage of growth, can influence the way different vegetation indices respond, a wide range of vegetation indices have been refined over time [15], with the objective of capturing as well as possible both intrinsic and extrinsic characteristics of plants.

NDVI is perhaps one of the most recognized and used vegetation indices. It

Figure 1: Sentinel-2 image (a) and PRISMA L2C image (b).

represents a composite measure that considers various vegetation-related factors, offering insights into different aspects of plant health and density. Examining NDVI values makes it possible to identify regions characterized by flourishing, stressed, or deteriorating vegetation. In agricultural applications, NDVI is applicable throughout the entire crop production cycle, except in cases where vegetation cover is extremely sparse, leading to insufficient spectral reflectance and tracking of variations in this index can facilitate timely interventions to improve plant health.

NDVI is calculated using the reflectance values of the near-infrared (NIR) and red (RED) spectral bands, see Equation (1) and its value range is from -1 to +1, with positive values closer to 1 signifying healthier and denser vegetation.

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED} \quad (1)$$

Given that various sensors can exhibit variations in spectral and spatial resolution, as well as radiometric calibration, it's important to be aware that NDVI can be sensitive to these discrepancies, and they can affect the accuracy and consistency of NDVI calculations when the data are coming from multiple sources. Additionally, atmospheric conditions can impact the reflectance values captured by remote sensors, meaning that the data might require atmospheric correction to ensure accurate NDVI values. In our case, as the hyperspectral sensor captured multiple bands in the RED and NIR region, for computing NDVI we used three strategies:

- (i) Band selection in the PRISMA images of the closest bands to the RED and NIR central wavelengths of sentinel B4 and B8. These are for PRISMA 664.8 nm for RED and 838.5 nm for NIR.
- (ii) An average of the RED and NIR bands in PRISMA images over the interval

[645.9 nm, 684.1 nm] and respectively [785.6 nm, 892.1 nm], similar to the spectral resolutions of the B4 and B8 bands for Sentinel-2 [16].

- (iii) A weighted average using a Gaussian function to the RED and NIR bands of PRISMA images over the same intervals as in the unweighted average calculation.

For comparison, NDVI was also computed on the Sentinel-2 image by selecting B8 for NIR and B4 for RED bands [17].

2.3 Color Palettes

For data visualization, especially numerical data, the chosen color palette must effectively differentiate between various types or categories of data, facilitating the understanding and assimilation of the information presented. The selection of the color palette is crucial because it influences the way data is interpreted and understood. That is why in remote sensing, where color plays an important role in data interpretation, the correct palette choice is vital for making informed decisions. Agricultural data, like NDVI, can be visualized using different color palettes to highlight variations and patterns. In this case, a suitable color palette often employs a color gradient from red (unhealthy) to green (healthy) to visualize the vitality of crops. In practice, the exact number of colors in an NDVI color palette can vary, from 2 or four colors to tens of color gradations, see some examples in Figure 2, contrasting pallet [18] and four-colors pallet, depending on the level of detail one wishes to perceive in NDVI maps. In this article, the sentinel color palette [19] in Figure 2 (a) was used for the visualization of NDVI maps.

Figure 2: Sentinel palette (a), contrasting palette (b), four-colors palette (c).

3 Results and discussions

For many remote sensing applications, including the computation and interpretation of vegetation indices, the atmospheric correction of multi- and hyper-

Figure 3: NDVI color maps for Sentinel-2 (column a) and PRISMA products using strategies (i) - column (b), (ii) column (c) and (iii) column (d) described in section 2.2. On the top row are the results for L1, on the middle row from L2B and the bottom row of L2C PRISMA products.

spectral pictures is a crucial first step. As previously mentioned, in the case of the images used in this study, different variations of the images with various atmospheric corrections are used. Our experiments started with an interpretation of these images with different levels of correction.

This section presents the experimental results on the chosen images in Figure 3 for the two images and various product levels. Some additional levels of processing seem to give results closer to what can be interpreted visually. Each representation can be useful for interpretation, and in order to decide which is more accurate, some on-site measurements could help to delineate a way forward. We expect these measurements to confirm that the neater the images are, the more valuable the results will be from an NDVI calculation perspective.

Thus, in Figure 4 are illustrated histograms on NDVI values for the images with corrections. Therefore, for PRISMA all three strategies give similar results, which can be seen in the overlap in the histogram. In the Sentinel-2 case, we only have available images with a first level of atmospheric correction. For PRISMA L1 the shape of the histogram remains similar to Sentinel-2, but as we add processing levels to PRISMA L2B and L2C, the PRISMA histogram shifts towards a most optimistic NDVI, the one for healthy plants, associated with green color. So, it can also be seen that after having the additional corrections, the assessment is already more optimistic than the Sentinel-2.

Figure 4: NDVI histograms for Sentinel-2 (blue color) and PRISMA L1 (a), L2B (b), L2C (c) using strategies (i) - red color, (ii) - green color, (iii) - yellow color.

4 Conclusions

As more and more HS data becomes publicly available, they can be used to develop products for precision agriculture. The spectral fingerprint, especially the information in the RED and NIR bands, can provide essential information for the early detection of problems in crop development. Thus, vegetation indices like NDVI can be used with success in this process. The question is how to compute the NDVI using HS images from different sources, as the different sensors acquire different wavelengths for RED and NIR bands. Furthermore, atmospheric conditions can influence the acquisition of the images. Our results show that different sensors and different product levels influence the calculation of the NDVI and, thus, the interpretation of crop health. In our case, the product level L2C from PRISMA offers a more optimistic estimation of the NDVI, while the product L2A of the Sentinel-2 image represents a rather pessimistic situation. The three proposed strategies to compute NDVI on HS images lead to very similar results in the case of the PRISMA data. To obtain reliable information that farmers can use, it is necessary to validate the results with infield measurements to choose the most appropriate source and the best product level for this task.

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